

Synthesis of 1,2,3-Benzotriazoles. Some 2-(4'-Chloro)- and (3',4'-Dichloro)-phenyl-1,2,3-benzotriazoles

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In continuation of the work going on in this laboratory on the behaviour of halogenopolynitrobenzenes¹⁻³, the present investigations include the preparation of a few 2-(4'-chloro)- (Table I) and (3',4'-dichloro)-phenyl-1,2,3-benzotriazoles (Table II), obtained by the condensation of halogenonitrobenzenes with 4-chloro- and 3,4-dichloro-phenylhydrazine, respectively. The reaction takes place with the elimination of a molecule of hydrochloric acid, forming a hydrazobenzene derivative which cyclises to 2-phenyl-1,2,3-benzotriazole-1-oxide. In ethanolic solution 1-oxide is reduced to 2-phenyl-1,2,3-benzotriazole². No attempt was made to isolate the intermediate products of the reaction.

TABLE I

2-Phenyl-1,2,3-benzotriazoles from 4-chlorophenylhydrazine

S. No.	Halogenonitrobenzene used.	2-(4'-Chlorophenyl-1,2,3-benzotriazole).	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	% Chlorine Found.	% Chlorine Reqd.
1	1-Chloro-2,4-dinitro.	6-Nitro.	172°	Light brown	C ₁₂ H ₇ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	12.69	12.93
2	1-Chloro-2, 6-dinitro.	4-Nitro.	220°	Brown	C ₁₂ H ₇ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	12.90	12.93
3	1-Chloro-2,4,6-trinitro.	4, 6-Dinitro.	183°	Dark brown	C ₁₂ H ₆ O ₃ N ₄ Cl	10.98	11.11
4	1, 2-Dichloro-4,6-dinitro.	4-Chloro-6-nitro.	160°	Brown	C ₁₂ H ₆ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂	22.65	22.97
5	1-Chloro-2-bromo-4, 6-dinitro.	4-Bromo-6-nitro.	182°	Buff	C ₁₂ H ₆ O ₂ N ₄ ClBr	32.32*	32.67
6	1-Chloro-2-iodo-4,6-dinitro.	4-Iodo-6-nitro.	190°	Brown	C ₁₂ H ₆ O ₂ N ₄ ClI	40.49**	40.67
7	1, 3-Dichloro-4,6-dinitro.	5-Chloro-6-nitro.	165°	Buff	C ₁₂ H ₆ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂	22.59	22.97
8	1,4-Dichloro-2,6-dinitro.	6-Chloro-4-nitro.	177°	Dark brown	C ₁₂ H ₆ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂	22.52	22.97
9	1-Chloro-4,6-dinitro-2-methyl.	6-Nitro-4-methyl.	192°	Brown	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	12.16	12.30
10	1-Chloro-4,6-dinitro-3-methyl.	6-Nitro-5-methyl.	190°	Buff	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	12.98	12.30
11	1-Chloro-2,6-dinitro-4-methyl.	4-Nitro-6-methyl.	185°	Light brown	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	12.12	12.30
12	1-Chloro-2, 4,6-trinitro-3-methyl.	4, 6-Dinitro-7-methyl.	187°	Yellow	C ₁₃ H ₈ O ₃ N ₄ Cl	10.25	10.64
13	1,2,3-Trichloro-4,6-dinitro.	4, 5-Dichloro-6-nitro.	205°	Fawn	C ₁₂ H ₅ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₃	30.74	30.80
14	2-Chloro-1,3-dibromo-4,6-dinitro.	4-Chloro-5-bromo-6-nitro.	215°	Light brown	C ₁₂ H ₅ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂ Br	39.04*	38.02
15	1,2,5-Trichloro-4,6-dinitro.	4, 7-Dichloro-6-nitro	188°	Silver grey	C ₁₂ H ₅ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₃	30.63	30.80
16	2, 5-Dichloro-1-bromo-4,6-dinitro.	"	188°	Do]	"	30.68	30.80

N.B.—All melting points are uncorrected.

* Refers to Cl+Br.

** " " to Cl+I.

1. Gupta and Garg, *this Journal*, 1964, 41, 62.

2. Joshi and Gupta, *ibid.*, 1958, 35, 681.

3. Joshi and Deorha, *ibid.*, 1952, 29, 545.

TABLE II

2-Phenyl-1,2,3-benzotriazoles from 3,4-dichlorophenylhydrazine.

*S. No.	2-(3',4'-Dichloro)phenyl-1,2,3-benzotriazole	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	%Chlorine.	
					Found.	Reqd.
1	6-Nitro.	108°	Brown	C ₁₂ H ₆ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂	22.78	22.97
2	4-Nitro.	107°	Yellow	C ₁₂ H ₆ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂	22.88	22.97
3	4, 6-Dinitro.	270°d	Dark brown	C ₁₂ H ₅ O ₄ N ₄ Cl ₂	19.85	20.05
4	4-Chloro-6-nitro.	176°	Tan	C ₁₂ H ₅ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₃	30.64	31.00
5	4-Bromo-6-nitro.	185°	Brick-red	C ₁₂ H ₅ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂ Br	38.67†	38.80
6	4-Iodo-6-nitro.	170°	Brown	C ₁₂ H ₅ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂ I	45.63**	45.61
7	5-Chloro-6-nitro	180°	Sepia	C ₁₂ H ₅ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₃	30.88	31.00
8	6-Chloro-4-nitro.	190°	Light brown	C ₁₂ H ₅ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₃	30.84	31.00
9	6-Nitro-4-methyl.	180°	Cream	C ₁₃ H ₈ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂	21.83	21.98
10	6-Nitro-5-methyl.	155°	Sepia	C ₁₃ H ₈ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂	21.74	21.98
11	4-Nitro-6-methyl.	198°	Light buff	C ₁₃ H ₈ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂	21.83	21.98
12	4,6-Dinitro-7-methyl.	142°	Brown	C ₁₃ H ₇ O ₄ N ₄ Cl ₂	19.19	19.32
13	4, 5-Dichloro-6-nitro.	225°	Light fawn	C ₁₂ H ₄ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₄	37.68	37.86
14	4-Chloro-5-bromo-6-nitro.	220°	Brown	C ₁₂ H ₄ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂ Br	43.56†	44.15
15	4, 7-Dichloro-6-nitro.	240°d	Light fawn	C ₁₂ H ₄ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₄	37.12	37.86
16	Do	240°d	Do	Do	37.28	37.60

*Number of halogenonitrobenzenes is the same as in Table I.

d denotes decomposition.

†Refers to Cl+Br.

** ,, Cl+I.

1,2,5-Trichloro-4,6-dinitrobenzene, when condensed with *p*-chlorophenylhydrazine, can provide three isomeric compounds: 2-(4'-chloro)phenyl-6,7-dichloro-4-nitro-, 2-(4'-chloro)phenyl-4,7-dichloro-6-nitro-, and 2-(4'-chloro)phenyl-5,6-dichloro-4-nitro-1,3-benzotriazoles. Only one isomer has, however, been obtained which is found to be identical with the product furnished by the condensation of 2,5-dichloro-1-bromo-4,6-dinitrobenzene with *p*-chlorophenylhydrazine. It is therefore 4,7-dichloro-6-nitro-2-(4'-chloro)phenyl-1,2,3-benzotriazole. This is in agreement with the formation of 4,7-dichloro-6-nitro-2-*p*-tolyl-1,2,3-benzotriazole by the condensation of *p*-tolylhydrazine with 1,2,5-trichloro-4,6-dinitrobenzene⁹.

Similarly, 3,4-dichlorophenylhydrazine afforded identical products with 1,2,5-trichloro-4,6-dinitro- and 2,5-dichloro-1-bromo-4,6-dinitro-benzenes. It is therefore 4,7-dichloro-6-nitro-2-(3',4'-dichloro)phenyl-1,2,3-benzotriazole.

In the formation of benzotriazoles and other heterocyclic compounds from reactive halogenonitrotoluene, it has been observed that the nitro group in *ortho* position to the

methyl group is always the one involved in the cyclisation³⁻⁴. Thus 1-chloro-2,4,6-trinitro-3-methylbenzene provided 2-(4'-chloro-)phenyl- and 2-(3',4'-dichloro-)phenyl-4,6-dinitro-7-methylbenzotriazoles when condensed with 4-chloro- and 3,4-dichloro-phenylhydrazine, respectively.

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